

RNA-Seq Transcriptomic Profiling

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Protocol description

This protocol describes the preparation of RNA samples from cell lines generated at CeMM for Illumina based high-throughput sequencing using polyA-enriched library preparation.

Materials

<p>Reagents:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Broad Range Quant-iT RNA Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific - # Q10213) ▪ Standard Sensitivity Total RNA DNF-471-33 Kit (Agilent - # DNF-471-0500) ▪ Nuclease-free Water (Ambion #AM9938) ▪ NEBNext Ultra II Directional RNA Library Prep Kit for Illumina (New England Biolabs #E7760) ▪ NEBNext Poly(A) mRNA Magnetic Isolation Module (New England Biolabs #E7490) ▪ NEBNext Multiplex Oligos for Illumina (New England Biolabs #E7600) ▪ Ampure XP beads (Beckman Coulter, #63882) ▪ Ethanol 96% Molecular grade (Sigma Aldrich, #51976) ▪ EB Buffer (Qiagen, #19086) ▪ High Sensitivity dsDNA Quanti-iT Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #Q33120) ▪ High Sensitivity Small Fragment DNF-477 Kit (Agilent, #DNF-477-0500) ▪ Qubit 1x dsDNA High Sensitivity (HS) Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific, # Q33231) ▪ PhiX Control v3 (Illumina, #FC-110-3001) ▪ NaOH 10M (Sigma Aldrich, BCCB8998) ▪ 1M Tris pH 8.0 Invitrogen (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #AM9855G) ▪ NovaSeq 6000 S4 Reagent Kit v1.5 (200 cycles) (Illumina, #20028313)
<p>Equipment:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cytation 5 multi-mode microplate reader BioTek (Agilent) ▪ Fragment Analyzer 96-channel (Agilent) ▪ MicroLab STAR (Hamilton) ▪ Biomek i7 Hybrid (Beckman Coulter) ▪ ViaFlo Handheld pipette system (Integra) ▪ epMotion 96 (Eppendorf) ▪ KingFisher Flex (Thermo Fisher Scientific) ▪ KF Flex 96 DW Magnetic Head (ThermoFisher Scientific) ▪ Mastercycler x50s (Eppendorf) ▪ Synergy HTX (BioTek) ▪ Qubit Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

	▪ NovaSeq 6000 Sequencing System (Illumina)
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Reagents setup

RNA samples were delivered to the Genomics Lab on dry ice in semi-skirted 96-well LoBind plates closed with 8-strip caps (Eppendorf).

Integrity and purity of input RNA play a critical role in the reliability of mRNA-seq when using Poly-A enrichment as library preparation method. Therefore, it is a good practice to perform quality control of the input RNA. Only samples with an RNA integrity number (RIN) above 7.5 were processed. Input RNA was set to 250ng.

Procedure

▪ RNA Quality Control and Normalization

1. Thaw RNA samples on ice.
2. To determine the RNA concentration: Take 2 μ L from each sample to quantify the RNA using the fluorescence-based Broad Range Quant-iT RNA Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). To measure the 96-well plate use a Cytation 5 multi-mode microplate reader (BioTek).
3. To determine the RNA integrity: Take 2 μ L from each sample to obtain the RIN value by running the Standard Sensitivity RNA Analysis DNF-471 Kit. To measure the 96-well plate we used a 96-channel Fragment Analyzer (Agilent).
4. Exclude samples with low RIN (less than 7.5) or low concentration (less than 5ng/ μ L).
5. Dilute the samples on a 96-well LoBind plate (Eppendorf) to 5ng/ μ L in 50 μ L (250ng Input RNA) with Nuclease-Free-Water using with a MicroLab STAR (Hamilton) pipetting robot.
6. Start library preparation procedure immediately or store the 96-well plate at -80°C using Microseal 'B' Adhesive Seals (BioRad, #MSB1001EDU) to seal the plate.

▪ Library Preparation: Automated and Manual Protocol

7. Library construction was performed with the NEBNext Ultra II Directional RNA Library Prep Kit for Illumina (#E7760), together with the NEBNext Poly(A) mRNA Magnetic Isolation Module (#E7490) upstream and the NEBNext Multiplex Oligos for Illumina (#E7600) downstream (all New England Biolabs). The only deviation from the manufacturer's protocol was the use of Ampure XP beads (Beckman Coulter) in the post-cDNA, post-ligation and post-PCR purification steps, instead of the recommended SPRIselect Beads. Also, an additional post-PCR purification (0.9x) was introduced to eliminate thoroughly remanent adaptor dimers in the preparation that could affect the sequencing efficiency afterwards.

1. To adapt the protocol to an **Automated**¹ 96-well plate system the following variations were introduced:

- a. Automated libraries were prepared on a Biomek i7 Hybrid automated liquid handler (Beckman Coulter). The Biomek i7 platform used here features two gripper arms, a 96-channel head as well as an independent multichannel Span-8. The 45-position deck includes an orbital shaker, cooling Peltiers, a tip-washing station, and an integrated thermal cycler (ATC).
 - b. The automated NEBNext Directional Ultra II RNA Library preparation method was initiated via the the Beckman Coulter Biomek 5 software method interface containing step-by-step instructions for the Biomek deck setup. Briefly:
 - 96-sample run
 - On-deck thermocycler
 - mRNA isolation module
 - 15 min. Fragmentation time
 - All wells use same adaptor dilution
 - No size selection
 - Automatic Index transfer
 - Custom PCR plate with Dual Index primers
 - Double Clean-up after PCR
 - c. Following the NEB reagent preparation and deck setup, the automated protocol was initiated and the Biomek i7 hybrid workstation performed the library preparation steps, including the incubation steps, without any user interaction.
 - d. All poly-A enrichment and enzymatic reactions were performed on the integrated on-deck Thermocycler ATC Applied Biosystems (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
 - e. Index PCR was performed with 13 cycles.
 - f. Final library was eluted in 25µL.
2. To adapt the protocol to a **Manual** 96-well plate system the following variations were introduced (This adaptation was necessary due to the unavailability of plastic consumables needed to run the Biomek i7 instrument during covid pandemic):
- a. For mixing and transferring reagents in 96-well plates system we used:
 - Benchtop ViaFlo (Integra) handheld pipette system using either a 384-channel pipetting head (12.5µL and 125µL) or a 96-channel pipetting head (300µL) for larger volumes.
 - epMotion 96 (Eppendorf) using 50µL and 300µL tips.
 - Speed and mixing times were adjusted on both systems according to reagent viscosity.
 - b. Post-cDNA purification and post-PCR purification was performed using the semi-automated KingFisher Flex (Thermo Fisher) adapted with DeepWell magnetic head. (Custom Program: Ampure_Flex_96DW_short)
 - c. All poly-A enrichment and enzymatic reactions were performed on an Eppendorf x50s Master cycler.
 - d. Index PCR was performed with 12 cycles.
 - e. Final library was eluted in 35µL.

3. After library preparation is complete, proceed to Library Quality Control or store libraries at -20°C for up to 8 weeks.

▪ **Library Quality Control**

1. If samples are frozen, thaw library samples on ice.
2. To determine the library concentration: Take 2µL from each sample to quantify the libraries using the fluorescence-based High Sensitivity dsDNA Quanti-iT Assay Kit (ThermoFisher). To measure the 96-well plate we used a Synergy HTX microplate reader (BioTek).
3. To determine the library size: Take 2µL from each sample to obtain the size of the library by running the High Sensitivity Small Fragment DNF-477 Kit. To measure the 96-well plate we used a 96-channel Fragment Analyzer (Agilent).
4. Samples with library concentration lower than 5nM and library size higher than 600pb or lower than 300bp were excluded
5. Dilute the samples on a 96-well LoBind plate (Eppendorf) to 5nM with EB-Buffer using with a MicroLab STAR (Hamilton) pipetting robot.
6. Pool all normalized libraries in a 1.5mL LoBind tube (Eppendorf) using a Biomek i7 instrument.
7. Proceed directly to sequencing. Alternatively freeze Pool at -20°C for up to 2 weeks.

▪ **mRNA Sequencing**

1. Bring the pool to room temperature if the pool is frozen.
2. Spike in 10nM PhiX control (Illumina) at 1% (v/v).
3. Measure the pool concentration using Qubit HS ds DNA Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific) on a Qubit Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and dilute with EB buffer to a final concentration of 0.7nM.
4. Bring sequencing NovaSeq S4 Flow cell to room temperature
5. Thaw Sequencing chemistry cartridges (NovaSeq6000- S4-SBS Cartridge - 200 cycles and NovaSeq6000 – Cluster Cartridge – S4) in a Water bath.
6. Acquire NovaSeq S4 Reagent Cartridge.
7. Dilute 10N NaOH (Sigma) to 0.2N NaOH and 1M Tris (pH 8, Ambion) to 400mM Tris using Nuclease-Free-Water (Ambion)
8. Denature Pool with 0.2N NaOH according to Illumina´s instructions.
9. Neutralize NaOH with Tris according to Illumina´s instructions.
10. Load denatured pool into Illumina Library Tube. Load Library tube into the corresponding slot in the S4 Cluster Cartridge
11. Load Flow Cell, Reagent Cartridge, SBS cartridge and Cluster Cartridge in the NovaSeq6000 instrument.
12. Input Run Settings as follows:

- a. Standard run
- b. Run name: input ID of the Flow Cell
- c. Sequencing Parameters: Read 1: 51; Read 2: 51; Index1: 8; Index2: 8.

13. Start Run.

Additional notes

Data availability

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards/transcriptomics/analysis/>
<https://re-solute.eu/resources/datasets>

References

1. Santacruz D, Enane FO, Fundel-Clemens K, Giner M, Wolf G, Onstein S, Klimek C, Smith Z, Wijayawardena B, Viollet C. Automation of high-throughput mRNA-seq library preparation: a robust, hands-free and time efficient methodology. **SLAS Discov. 2022 Mar;27(2):140-147.** doi: 10.1016/j.slasd.2022.01.002. Epub 2022 Jan 16. PMID: 35093290.

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